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**CAIRT mission product test data set descriptions for
impact study Stratosphere/UTLS and weather and
climate predictability**

README-5

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<i>Abstract</i> This document describes the simulated CAIRT L2 profiles of O ₃ and H ₂ O used as test dataset-product (TDS-P) used in the data assimilation study on NWP prediction.		
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List of acronyms

ACT	ACross Track
ALT	ALong Track
AK	Averaging Kernel
BASCOE	Belgian Assimilation System for Chemical Observations
CAIRT	Changing Atmosphere Infra-Red Tomography explorer
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium range Weather Forecast
EnKF	Ensemble Kalman Filter
FL2S	Fast Level 2 Simulator
LPE	Linear Performance Estimation
MAO	Model At Observation
MIAP	Mission Impact Assessment Plan
MLS	Microwave Limb Souder
MLT	Mesosphere Lower Thermosphere
MO	Mission Objective of CAIRT
NR	Nature Run
NWP	Numerical Weather Prediction system
OD	Operational Data (i.e. operational analysis)
OSSE	Observing System Simulation Experiment
PerReC	CAIRT Performance and Requirement Consolidation study
SciReC	CAIRT Scientific and Requirement Consolidation study
SO	Scientific Objective of CAIRT
STE	Stratosphere-Troposphere Exchange
TDS-P	Test Data Set-Product
UTLS	Upper Troposphere Lower Stratosphere
WP	Work Package (of PerReC if no other project mentioned)

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1 Introduction

The purpose of this document is to provide a description of the test data set product (TDS-P) produced for the CAIRT impact study Stratosphere/UTLS and weather and climate prediction during the CAIRT Performance and Requirement Consolidation study. Here, TDS-P are simulated CAIRT L2 profiles produced following this chain of processes:

1. Select a model Nature Run (NR) providing reference atmosphere for O₃ and possibly H₂O
2. Regridding NR onto the CAIRT retrieval grid, leading to NR@CAIRT
3. Simulate CAIRT L2 profiles given NR@CAIRT, the Fast Level 2 Simulator (FL2S) and the Linear Performance Estimation (LPE) files of CAIRT

These steps are defined in Sect. 2. The file format of CAIRT NetCDF-CF is described in Sect. **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** The codes and configuration files used to produce this NetCDF-CF are stored on the BIRA-IASB subversion system or the FZJ git repository as detailed in the different subsections of this document and in Sect. 4.

2 Simulating CAIRT L2 profiles

2.1 The Nature Run (NR)

The nature run for ozone and water vapour we have used is the ECMWF operational analysis (OD, D for data) retrieved on a horizontal Gaussian grid N256 (i.e. around 40 km horizontal resolution), with 137 vertical levels with a vertical resolution around 500 m in the UTLS and decreasing toward the surface and has 6-hourly. ECWmf OD is stored in the ECMWF MARS archiving system and Table 1 provides the MARS parameters to retrieve it. In this case, the subset of OD (in GRIB file format) is stored on the ECMWF compute server.

Cloud fractions, necessary to flag out CAIRT data in presence of clouds are also taken from OD.

The retrieval of GRIB file is at ECMWF using two shell scripts, the first calling (mars2sbatch.sh) the second one (mars_nr.sh). The first script is looping over the days for a request period given at input and call the second script which run on the ECMWF batch system (i.e. allowing processing multiple days at the same time). The command is the following (code versions are discussed in Sect.4):

```
> mars2sbatch.sh $YYYYmmddHHMM_start $YYYYmmddHHMM_end
```

Where YYYY=year, mm=month, dd=day, HH=hour (possible values are 0, 6, 12 and 18) and MM=minutes (should be always 0). For example, for January 2021, one should have

```
YYYYmmddHHMM_start=202101010000 and YYYYmmddHHMM_end=202101311800
```

Table 1: Information to access to CAMS OD experiment on the ECMWF MARS system for a given date where YYYY-MM-DD and hour HH.

class	od
expver	1
stream	oper
type	an
levelist	1/to/137
levtype	ml
params	Insp/t/q/o3/cc*
date	YYYY-MM-DD
time	HH
grid	F256

* The list of parameters are: Insp=log of surface pressure, t=temperature, q=specific humidity, o3=ozone and cc=cloud fractions.

2.2 Regridding the nature run onto the CAIRT retrieval grid (NR@CAIRT)

The regridding of NR onto the CAIRT L2 retrieval grid is done using a subset of the BASCOE system, namely BASCOE-MAO (Model At Observation). BASCOE being a data assimilation system, it includes libraries to read model fields and observation files, and an observation operator to interpolate the model fields at the geolocation of the observations. In its MAO configuration, model fields are taken from snapshot files instead of being simulated by the BASCOE model. (This is the procedure used to validate stratospheric ozone from CAMS analysis and forecast in the CAMS Evaluation and Quality Control – EQC – project, namely CAMS2_82, see, e.g. Schoenhardt et al., 2023.)

Here, the model fields are the ECMWF OD 6-hourly snapshot files. The CAIRT L2 retrieval grid for the period December 2020 – March 2021 is produced using the CAIRT retrieval grid simulator (sim_CAIRT_grid.py developed during Phase 0 and available at https://jugit.fz-juelich.de/cairt-scirec/sim_CAIRT_grid). This code uses as input the CAIRT orbit simulated in Phase 0 for one year and stored on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10262729>). Here, the CAIRT retrieval grid assumes a swath of 500 km with 25 km ACT sampling. Downgrading this resolution to the CAIRT swath and ACT resolution is done in FL2S (see the ATBD of the Scientific Work Bench, Höpfner et al., 2025).

The procedure is then the following. For each day:

1. produce CAIRT retrieval grid files with time and location of the retrieved profiles using the sim_CAIRT_grid.py. In order to allow parallel production of files, this script is launched using two other scripts. simGrid.sh is preparing the environment to allow sim_GRID_grid.py to run on the ECMWF batch system for a single day while simGrid2sbatch.sh is looping on the day of the period and call simGrid.sh every day.
2. run the script mao.sh which call BASCOE-MAO, where species and cloud fraction from OD 6-hourly snapshots of one day are interpolated onto the CAIRT retrieval grid. These files are called NR@CAIRT (or NR@CAIRT). On top of this script, we have mao2sbatch.sh which loop on each day of the period and launch mao.sh on the ECMWF batch system allowing for parallel computation.

All the versions of these scripts and codes are given in Sect. 4

```
> ./simGrid2sbatch.sh $YYYYmmdd_start $YYYYmmdd_end  
> ./mao2sbatch.sh $YYYYmmdd_start $YYYYmmdd_end
```

Where YYYY=year, mm=month, dd=day.

2.3 Perturbing NR@CAIRT using LPE and FL2S and production of CAIRT L2 NetCDF files

The daily files of NR interpolated onto the CAIRT retrieval grid (i.e. NR@CAIRT) are perturbed and smoothed according to CAIRT errors from Linear Performance Estimation (LPE v3), done using FL2S (v 0.9.3dev0 and described in the SWB ATBD, Höpfner et al., 2025).

Given NR@CAIRT daily file and LPE files, FL2S simulates CAIRT simulated L2 profiles of O₃ and H₂O. A quality flag is created to account for could contamination in FL2S, and the scenario file cloud_impact_cth5-22_0.003.dat, described in (Höpfner et al., 2025).

For this TDS-P, the FL2S codes are using the configuration file `config_CAIRT-PhA-IS50.py`. This config file defines, in particular, the setup for producing initial seed for uncorrelated random number generation. The initial seed value is saved in each daily TDS-P to ensure reproductibility. The FL2S codes, the config file and the cloud scenario `cloud_impact_cth5-22_0.003.dat` are stored on the FZJ git repository or the BIRA-IASB subversion system (see Sect. 4). The config file is also given in Sect. 4. For each day, the following call is made:

```
> ./fl2s_run.py -OA -f NR@CAIRT_file -o CAIRT_L2_filename config_CAIRT-PhA-IS50.py
```

For this TDS-P, the FL2S codes are using the configuration file `config_CAIRT-PhA-IS50.py`. This config file defines, in particular, the setup for producing initial seed for uncorrelated random number generation. The initial seed value is saved in each daily TDS-P to ensure reproductibility. The FL2S codes, the config file and the cloud scenario `cloud_impact_cth5-22_0.003.dat` are stored on the FZJ git repository (see Sect. 5). For each day, the following call is made:

Given NR@CAIRT daily file and LPE files, FL2S simulates CAIRT L2 profiles of O₃ and H₂O. A quality flag is created to account for cloud contamination, using `make_CSS_cloud_impact.py` and the scenario file `cloud_impact_cth5-22_0.003.dat`.

For this TDS-P, the FL2S codes are using the configuration file `config_CAIRT-PhA-IS50.py` (the config file is also given in Sect. 4.). This config file defines, in particular, the setup for producing initial seed for uncorrelated random number generation. The initial seed value is saved in each daily TDS-P to ensure reproductibility. The command used to simulate daily CAIRT files and to include a quality flag due to presence of clouds is called by a main script `fl2s_2_sbatch.sh` which loop on each day of a requested period and launch daily computations on the ECMWF batch system allowing for parallel production. The command is the following:

```
> ./fl2s_2_sbatch.sh $YYYYmmdd_start $YYYYmmdd_end
```

Note that CAIRT L2 files are created in the NOB file format described in the SWB ATBD.

3 Conversion to BURP

To be filled by Beatriz.

4 Versions, traceability and reproducibility

The codes and configuration files used to produce this TDS-P up to NetCDF files are either on the BIRA-IASB subversion system or on the FZJ CAIRT git repository. In the first case, all codes are below the following directory: <https://svn-intern.aeronomie.be/ae/COMMON>, in the second case, all codes are in `jugit.fz-juelich.de:cairt-scirec`. Code names, their corresponding processes, their location in the subversion/git system and their revision numbers are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Code names, their corresponding processes, their location in the subversion/git system and their revision numbers. All codes are available under <https://svn-intern.aeronomie.be/ae/COMMON>.

Code/config name	Process	Code location (svn means on the BIRA-IASB subversion system; git mean on the FZJ git repository)	revision number
mars2sbatch.sh, mars_nr.sh	NR retrieval	(svn) stand-alone/CAIRT/PhA/IS50/1_NR	13083
simGrid2sbatch.sh simGrid.sh sim_CAIRT_grid.py	CAIRT retrieval grid simulation	(svn) stand-alone/CAIRT/PhA/IS50/2_simGRID	13083
mao2sbatch.sh, mao.sh	Regridding NR onto the CAIRT retrieval grid	(svn) stand-alone/CAIRT/PhA/IS50/3_mao	13083
BASCOE-MAO exec	Regridding NR onto the CAIRT retrieval grid, called by mao.sh	(svn) atmos/bascop/branches/qe10.00.00	13083
fl2s_2_sbatch.sh, fl2s.sh, make_CSS_cloud_impact.py, config file for FL2S	simulation of CAIRT L2 profiles	(svn) stand-alone/CAIRT/PhA/IS50/4_fl2s	13083
fl2s_run.py, fl2s.py	simulation of CAIRT L2 profiles	(git) cairt_fl2s/cairt_fl2s_bira_1	5ad46a2a

Content of config_CAIRT-PhA-IS50.py:

```
para2ref = {
  'h2o': '_mrd_thres_ref_1',
  'o3': '_mrd_thres_ref_2',
}

lpe_ncdir = "/ec/res4/hpcperm/cui/CAIRT/lpe_v3_mrd_thres/"

CSSn = 'IS50'

mod_ncdir = "/home/quentin/CAIRT/data_t2/CSS/CSS7-SHW/css7shw2"

# define fl2s parameters
sol_activity = 0 # solar activity index (within 0 for low activity and 1 for high activity). The default is 0.
n_cal = 56 # calibration period length (in terms of acquisitions). The default is 100.
akd_threshold = 0.003 # averaging kernel threshold. The default is 0.003.
ak_noise_sys = {
  'ak':{'noi':False,'sys':False},
  'aknoi':{'noi':True,'sys':False},
  'aksys':{'noi':False,'sys':True},
  'aknoisys':{'noi':True,'sys':True},
}

# define across-track bins for different across-track averaging lengths of the lpe
act_bin_ind = {
  100:[[2,6],[6,10],[10,14],[14,18]],
  300:[[2,14],[2,14],[6,18],[6,18]],
}

# random generator seed method
# - auto: fixed seed based on date and target name + `random_seed` (below)
# - fixed: uses `random_seed` for all targets and dates
# - random (or anything else): no specific seed used, gives non-reproducible results
random_seed_method = "auto"
```

```
# fixed random seed or extra "jitter" for "auto"
# random_seed = 1234
random_seed = np.random.randint(123456789)

# for faster test set to positive number to calculate only nmod_use samples along the tracks;
nmod_use = -100

css_config = {
    'IS50': dict(
    )
}

# Cloud mask information
cld_fraction_lim = 0.2 # Mask will be set for cloud fraction above cld_fraction_lim (if "cc" in model input
scenario file)
#cld_impact_file = "cloud_impact_cth5-16_0.003.dat"
#cld_impact_file = "cloud_impact_cth5-21_0.003.dat"
cld_impact_file = "cloud_impact_cth5-22_0.003.dat" # The most stringent case

# Path to temporary directory
scratch="/ec/res4/scratch/cui/CAIRT/tmp/"
```